

In-situ gradient formation by direct solid addition of buffer components

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ABSTRACT

Buffer preparation and storage requires a significant facility footprint in large scale bioprocessing and together with the costs of supply chain management can have a substantial economic impact. In-line buffer mixing in chromatography is commonly performed by blending different buffer solutions using at least two pumps and a static or dynamic mixer. We developed a device for an in-line gradient delivery of buffering agents directly from solids to be applied for chromatographic separation processes. A solid feeding device with a screw conveyor and a hold tank for the solids was designed and a miniaturized system was 3D printed. The coefficient of variation for the precision of the solid feeding of 5 different buffering agents was below 5% even for very small solid flow rates necessary for lab-scale chromatography. Stability was demonstrated by a constant linear solid feed at a very low dosing rate of 0.05 g.min⁻¹ over 24 hours. We demonstrated the suitability for chromatography by directly connecting the system to a standard chromatography workstation for protein chromatography. The solids were fed into a miniaturized continuously stirred tank reactor connected to an ÄKTA purification system. The performance of the in-line gradient delivery of buffering agents directly from solids was compared to conventional in-line buffer mixing. We were able to achieve highly linear gradients for elution using only one pump of a chromatographic system, generating the gradient by the direct addition of solids avoiding the necessity of additional pumps and hold tanks. By direct conditioning of buffers and the addition of solids a simple, just in time, at site preparation of buffers was possible. The design of the feeding unit for solid addition for buffer preparation is easily scalable and adaptable to work with or as a replacement for already existing in-line dilution or conditioning units.

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1. Introduction

Buffer preparation and storage has a substantial economic impact for the production of biopharmaceuticals [1]. A significant facility footprint is required and the costs of supply chain management is substantial but often overlooked [2]. The preparation of a buffer direct from solid ingredients is the optimal way to reduce footprint and improve the supply chain. Gradient delivery in chromatography is usually done by blending different buffer solutions using at least two pumps and a dynamic or static mixer [3,4]. The accuracy of buffer preparation is mainly influenced by the pre-column volume of the system. This effect has an especially high impact on the gradient quality at very small scale [5,6]. The buffers

for blending are either made from solids batch-wise and stored until use or diluted from stock solution. However, the stock solution has to be prepared from solids and stored as well. In particular, the necessary buffer preparation and storage is known to lead to an extensively large facility in bioprocesses, but also to a large ecological footprint and excessive use of resources [7,8]. Whether bioprocesses are operated continuously or in batch, the contribution from the preparation and storage of process liquids is still one of the most resource demanding operations [9]. To cope with this challenge, approaches like buffer recycling, buffer outsourcing, in-line dilution as well as in-line conditioning have been proposed and developed [9,10]. For in-line dilution systems, a concentrated buffer solution is automatically diluted with water for injection (WFI) to the desired conditions and stored in an intermediate hold tank. Whereas, in-line conditioning systems enable a direct delivery of e.g. a buffer into a chromatographic separation step and eventually offer a higher floor space reduction than in-line

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dilution [9,11]. Both strategies combined with single-use technology were shown to save time and reduce costs since cleaning of respective tanks is eliminated. Alternatively, strategies have been developed to implement in-line dilution systems while reducing the variety of buffers needed for a whole downstream train to a minimum as realized by the ASAP process [12,13]. It was also shown that chromatographic systems can be fully automated for the use with in-line dilution [11,14,15]. Moreover, by integration of individual chromatography systems into an external controller a complete downstream process was implemented offering modularity and superior flexibility [16,17].

All these systems were developed to reduce the necessary stock solutions for buffer preparation as much as possible but are fundamentally limited by the solubility limit of each individual buffer as well as the number of stock solutions that can be kept in the facility. In addition, all these systems need delivery of the respective solutions to their point of use. Thus, an in-line gradient delivery of buffering agents directly from solids would increase the productivity of chromatography unit operations and minimize the cost of buffer preparation as well as storage. Solubility is of course no limitation for the storage of solids and the on-demand preparation at the point of use avoids necessary storage facilities, delivery systems for stock solutions or buffers, and tanks for holding different kinds of buffers or buffer stock solutions. In addition, it reduces the waste of material by on-demand preparation. Buffers are typically prepared in excess and parts that are not consumed are discarded. An at-site just in time preparation can reduce the environmental footprint of a chromatographic process drastically. In this study, we developed a device that allows a continuous direct solid feed addition for buffer preparation in chromatographic separations from lab scale to production scale. We evaluate the stability, accuracy and precision of the device in the solid feeding of various buffering agents. Ultimately, we demonstrate a proof of concept for an in-line gradient delivery of buffering reagents directly from solids or crystals in chromatographic separation steps.

2. Material and methods

All chemicals were of analytical grade and purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA), unless stated otherwise. All gradient elution and capture experiments were performed using an ÄKTA Pure 25 system (Cytiva, Uppsala, Sweden).

2.1. Experimental set-up

The solid feeding device was designed using Autodesk Inventor 2019 (Autodesk, San Rafael, CA, USA) and 3D printed by Sculpteo (Villejuif, France) or in-house using an Anycubic Photon S (Shenzhen, China) 3D printer and designed as a miniaturized screw conveyor driven by stepper motors (Stepperonline, Nanjing, China). The device was controlled by a minicomputer Raspberry Pi 3 (Raspberry Pi Foundation, Cambridge, United Kingdom) programmed using Python (Python Software Foundation, Wilmington, United States). For stability, precision and accuracy experiments the design of the hopper was optimized in regard to geometric shape. The solid compound was put into the storage tank of the feeding device and calibration experiments were conducted for sodium chloride (NaCl), tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (Tris), sodium citrate monohydrate, polyethylen glycol 6000 (PEG 6000) and sodium acetate (NaAc) (Supporting information – Table S1). The calibration experiments were performed using an Entris® Precision balance (Sartorius, Göttingen, Germany) connected to the Raspberry Pi 3. The data was collected on-line using the Simple Data Logger software (Smartlux SARL, Born, Luxembourg). For chromatographic experiments, the solids were fed into a miniaturized continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) with a magnetic stir-

rer and bottom outlet. This reactor was connected to a short tubular reactor filled with static mixers and further connected to the ÄKTA purification system. A 0.2 µm syringe filter was installed in-line a 200 µl loop tubing to ensure that no solid particles block the top filter of the column. However, after evaluating the set-up we noticed that all solid buffer components were immediately mixed. For that reason, we uninstalled the syringe filter and a pre-column pressure increase could not be observed over the whole duration of the cycles. Absorbance of UV and conductivity was measured using the sensors of the ÄKTA system. Conductivity and osmolality was confirmed using an offline MC226 conductivity meter (Mettler Toledo, Columbus, United States) and an OsmoTech® single sample osmometer (Advanced Instruments, Norwood, United States). The pH of the buffer solutions for both linear and step gradients was adjusted prior and confirmed manually at the end of the run. Traditional system setups and system setups for the presented device are shown in Fig. 1.

2.2. Salt gradient elution

Salt gradient elution experiments were carried out using Esh-muno CP-FT resin (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). Small scale experiments were performed using a prepacked Minichrom Esh-muno CP-FT resin with a volume of 1 mL. For the scale up a Tricorn™ 10 housing (Cytiva, Uppsala, Sweden) was used with a final column volume of 10 mL Esh-muno CP-FT resin. Equilibration-, wash and elution buffer were 50 mM phosphate buffer pH 6.9 and 50 mM phosphate buffer supplemented with 500 mM sodium chloride for the elution buffer. Before loading the column was equilibrated with 5 CV. Loading of the column was done using pulse injections with a loop volume of 100 µL. The feed concentration was 5 mg.mL⁻¹ of lysozyme and cytochrome c dissolved in the equilibration buffer supplemented with 50 mM sodium chloride, respectively. All buffers were prepared either batch wise or by in-line conditioning directly from solids by the presented solid buffer preparation device which were consequently compared based on osmolality, conductivity and final pH. Absorbance of the elution fraction was measured at 280 nm for lysozyme and 405 nm for cytochrome C. For the in-line preparation directly from solid, sodium chloride was fed directly into a beaker with a working volume of 100 mL of phosphate buffer containing no additional salt. Once the in-line preparation was initiated, linearity was achieved by setting the dosing rate accordingly to the duration of the gradient.

2.3. Step gradient elution

For step gradient elution experiments an immobilized metal affinity resin Ni Sepharose 6 Fast Flow (Cytiva, Uppsala, Sweden) resin was used. Step gradient experiments were performed in a Tricorn™ 10 housing (Cytiva, Uppsala, Sweden) with a column volume of 2.1 mL. Equilibration and wash buffer were 50 mM phosphate buffer pH 8.0 supplemented with 10 mM imidazole and 300 mM sodium chloride. The elution buffer was supplemented with imidazole to reach a concentration of 500 mM. Before loading, the column was equilibrated with 5 CV and washed after the loading step with 2 CV. Loading of the column was done using pulse injections with a loop volume of 100 µL. The feed concentration was 2.2 mg.mL⁻¹ of His-tagged green fluorescent protein (GFP) in the equilibration buffer. All buffers were prepared either batch wise or in-line by the presented solid buffer preparation device which were consequently compared based on osmolality, conductivity and final pH. Absorbance of the elution fraction was measured at 488 nm for GFP and 240 nm for blank gradient experiments. For the in-line preparation of equilibration buffer imidazole was fed based on a scale into a beaker to reach an equilibration buffer concentration of 10 mM imidazole. After loading of the sample onto the

Fig. 1. (A) Illustration of a commercially available ÄKTA chromatography workstation with a dynamic mixer for preparation of a binary gradient from two pre-prepared buffers solutions A and B. (B) Illustration of the adapted system with the in situ device for in-line conditioning using a single dual piston pump. The device is directly connected to the dual pump of the ÄKTA workstation via a short tubular reactor.

column additional imidazole was fed into the beaker to reach a target concentration of 500 mM imidazole.

3. Results and discussion

The concept of using solids directly to generate buffers and gradients on demand requires a device for continuously feeding solid buffer components. Screw conveyor devices have been described in the literature and are available for larger scale operation, but unfortunately no miniaturized system for the slow solid feeding rates necessary for lab-scale operation area was available. To circumvent this limitation, we used the now readily available additive manufacturing and designed a miniatures screw conveyor system, adapted for 3D printability and capable of delivering a very small continuous feed of solid components. The system consists of a screw conveyor and a feeding hopper as well as a mounting plate and connection to the driving stepper motor for the screw conveyor. The device was mounted with screws and connected to a stepper motor. The feeding of the screw conveyor was controlled by adjusting the motion of the stepper motor. Solid buffer species were introduced at the top of the screw conveyor to ensure a constant supply. The stepper motor was controlled through a simple custom build python script (Fig. 2).

As the system was designed from scratch and no prior knowledge was available for such small screw conveyor systems and the continuous transport of solids, a number of experiments to test the device for accuracy, precision and stability with and without connection to a chromatographic system and with several different buffer components were performed.

3.1. Precision, accuracy and stability

Precision and accuracy of solid dosing was evaluated by weight at different feeding speeds with sodium chloride, tris, sodium acetate, sodium citrate monohydrate, PEG6000 and imidazole all in crystal form. The speed of the feeder was varied between 20-120 rpm. For sodium chloride, the range was increased from 1-120 rpm for the evaluation of long-term dosing. The actual feeding range in terms of $\text{g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ differed between the tested chemicals. The range

Fig. 2. The 3D design of the developed device for in situ preparation from crystals or solids (1) with the Top (2), front (3) and side view (4).

of the dosing rate was therefore dependent on the kind of solid, presumably due to different particle size, particle roughness and other physical properties, and the speed of the feeder needs to be adjusted to the kind of crystals to achieve the same gravimetric

Fig. 3. (A) Dosing of five different buffering agents at various motor speeds ($n=5$). Colored points represent repeated dosing runs of sodium chloride ($n=50$) at three different motor speeds. (B) Dosing profile of sodium chloride at three different motor speeds. If error bars are not shown then the error bars are smaller than the symbol.

feeding rate. Fig. 3 – (A) shows that for all components except imidazole the standard deviation was below 5% for all tested feeder speeds (Table S1). Furthermore, we noticed that the dosing rate in grams per revolution was highly dependent on the hygroscopic characteristics and the resulting bridging formation in the hopper, limiting the amount of crystal that is picked up by the screw conveyor itself. This is a well-known phenomenon in bulk and solid handling which is caused by the geometry of the hopper and is more pronounced in miniaturized systems. This led to difficulties to perform calibration curves for imidazole and sodium citrate monohydrate. The recording of a calibration curve for imidazole was therefore unfortunately not accurate enough to provide reliable enough feeding rates for the purpose of gradient generation for chromatography in this miniaturized scale (data not shown). To circumvent this limitation, we implemented a closed loop control into the python script controlling the feeder to automatically readjust the screw conveyor speed during runtime by measuring the weight of the hopper and feeder system. For sodium citrate monohydrate regular manual tapping of the hopper resolved the issue of bridging formation and accurate and stable feeding rates were achieved (Fig. 3 – A). To avoid such issues on larger scale, multiple ways have been described in the literature ranging from specific hopper geometries, additional mixing in the hopper to manual removal of any bridging [18,19]. As this work concentrates on the application of the device for chromatography and not the hopper design, we opted for manual removal of bridging when necessary during runtime. However, we are certain that this shortcoming for hygroscopic compounds can be solved by either device scale up, hopper design or controlling environmental conditions as well as additives [19,20]. Here, we saw significant differences of feeding rates for the investigated buffer components and we recommend investigating the dosing accuracy in dependence of the environmental conditions such as ambient temperature, humidity and

moisture for each compound separately. While for Imidazole, an additional control by weight is necessary, it was not necessary to include additional control systems for any other compound. Since the calibration experiments resulted in a comparable performance throughout the various buffering agents, we tested the system on dosing accuracy and precision of repeated batches ($\text{g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, $n=50$) for three different motor speeds using sodium chloride. As illustrated in Fig. 3 – (B) all batches conducted at various motor speeds were in a $\pm 5\%$ range of the initial target dosing rate. Finally, to prove long term stability we performed a 24 h dosing at a very low dosing rate of $0.05 \text{ g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to evaluate the stability of the system using sodium chloride and showed the stability of solid feed flow (Figure – S1). As shown in Figure S1 a linear regression was performed over the duration of the feeding and using a confidence band of 95%. The standard error is very small ($<5\%$) and over a duration of 24h was comparable to the shorter dosing times performed prior. Therefore, we can conclude that the current design offers precise and accurate performance in short term and long term and is therefore suitable for gradient generation for individual chromatography runs as well as continuous long-term operation. Undoubtedly, there is still a need to further research on the design of the device for having a closed system which is an inevitable requirement for an industrial application but it would be out the scope of the proof of concept. Besides, that already existing equipment such as twin screw conveyors are commercially available in closed fashion, thus, minimizing the risk of contamination while allowing an adequate dust control.

3.2. Salt gradient elution

In order to demonstrate the application of the in-situ buffer preparation directly from solid buffer components we have performed a small-scale chromatography. A binary protein mixture

Fig. 4. Salt gradients generated by the in-situ preparation method directly from solid buffer components for the separation of lysozyme and cytochrome c. UV absorbance was monitored at 280 nm and conductivity by the built-in monitors of the ÄKTA workstation (n=5).

consisting of cytochrome c and lysozyme was separated on a 1 mL cation exchanger by a linear gradient. The tested solid feeder was mounted on top of a small dynamic mixer (Fig. 1 - B) connected to an ÄKTA Pure chromatography workstation. After sample application, a gradient elution was performed by adding salt in crystal form continuously to a liquid to achieve a gradient length of 10 CV. For evaluating the capability of the device to perform stable and linear gradients we repeated the gradient five consecutive times and evaluated the stability based on the elution peaks of lysozyme and cytochrome c, conductivity as well as final osmolality (Fig. 4). The formation of the gradient by our method is highly reproducible. This can be shown by the average and standard deviation of the conductivities at peak maximum. For elution of cytochrome c the average conductivity at peak maximum measured at 405 nm was $16.3 \pm 0.29 \text{ mS.cm}^{-1}$; measured at 280 nm $16.4 \pm 0.35 \text{ mS.cm}^{-1}$. This yields in a coefficient of variation of 1.7 and 1.8% respectively. For lysozyme we obtained a coeffi-

Table 1

Difference in elution conductivity between the in situ gradient formation by direct feeding of buffer components and conventional preparation of buffers for a 1 mL and 10 mL column. n.d. = not done.

Protein and column volume	Gradient length		
	5CV	10CV	20CV
	Difference in %		
Lysozyme (1 mL)	1.22 %	2.16 %	3.93 %
Cytochrome c (1 mL)	1.19 %	0.92 %	1.92 %
Lysozyme (10 mL)	0.30 %	n.d.	n.d.
Cytochrome c (10 mL)	4.53 %	n.d.	n.d.

cient of variation of 1.3% (Elution conductivity at peak maximum is $31.9 \pm 0.41 \text{ mS.cm}^{-1}$). We also measured the osmolality at the end of the gradient and observed a coefficient of variation ($947 \pm 18.2 \text{ mOsm.kg}^{-1}$) of 1.9 %. For comparison we also performed a conventional run using two pre-prepared buffers, and the gradient generation by pumps and in-line mixer which resulted in a final osmolality of $957 \pm 1.2 \text{ mOsm.kg}^{-1}$.

Then we tested the device to perform gradients with different lengths (5, 10 and 20 CVs) in 1 mL and 10 mL columns. The feeding rate was adjusted to the length of the gradient and the column volume. The salt gradients generated by the two systems pumps of the ÄKTA and the build-in mixer differed slightly at the beginning of the gradient (Fig. 5). The linearity of the gradient produced by the in-situ mixing from solid buffer components is comparable to the conventional buffer preparation (Fig. 5). The slightly different retention volumes of the eluted peaks are explained by the slightly different slopes of the gradients. The difference in retention volumes is extremely small (Table 1) and vanished when the feeding rate is adjusted.

The slight differences for both systems were addressed by recalibrating the solid feeding system before we scaled the method from 1 mL (Fig. 5 - A, C, D) columns to 10 mL columns leading to a much closer match between the two systems (Fig. 5 - B).

Fig. 5. Salt elution gradients of different length for the separation of lysozyme and cytochrome c at 280 at 405 nm absorbance at 1 mL (A, C and D) and 10 mL CV (B) using the ÄKTA (orange) and the device for in situ preparation from solid buffer components (blue), respectively.

Fig. 6. (A) Step elution gradients of imidazole performed by the ÄKTA (orange) and the device for in situ preparation from solid buffer components (blue) fed by weight. (B) Elution profile of imidazole performed by the ÄKTA and by in situ preparation from solid buffer components in unloaded column conditions at 240 nm absorbance. Dashed lines (orange, blue, grey) illustrate absorbance at (A) 488 nm and (B) 240 nm as well as the concentration profile of the elution buffer (grey).

The chromatograms are very similar irrespective of the method which is used for preparation of the buffers. The difference in the gradient shape are explained by the different dead volume, which is mainly determined by the dynamic mixer in conventional chromatography systems and by the static mixer in our system. A feedback control loop would help to generate theoretical gradient shapes [9,11,21].

3.3. Imidazole step elution

Imidazole is a very common buffer in metal chelate chromatography and therefore we selected such a buffer as model to demonstrate our in-situ gradient formation system. Besides linear gradients, we developed a methodology for the device to generate a step gradient. Once again, the device was mounted on a vessel filled with base buffer which was used for equilibration and sample application to the immobilized metal affinity chromatography column. After the equilibration a His-Tag GFP solution was loaded on the column by pulse injection. To generate the step gradient, imidazole was fed with maximum speed (200 rpm) into the buffer reservoir to reach 500 mM imidazole as fast as possible. The feeding was done by weight to ensure a steep gradient for elution due to the aforementioned hygroscopicity of imidazole. The ÄKTA was on pause over the duration of the feeding (10 minutes). Nevertheless, it is intriguing that the step gradient performed by the ÄKTA using the in-line mixer and the device for in situ preparation from solid buffer components approach resulted in almost identical chromatograms (Fig. 6 - A). These findings are further sup-

ported by the final osmolality of the equilibration (674.0 ± 3.28 mOsm.kg⁻¹ device for in situ formation from solid buffer components vs. 670.50 ± 14.41 mOsm.kg⁻¹ ÄKTA) and elution buffer (1160 ± 19.55 mOsm.kg⁻¹ device for in situ formation from solid buffer components vs. 1190.52 ± 1.70 mOsm.kg⁻¹), respectively. Since imidazole can be readily measured by UV absorbance, comparisons without protein solution were performed (Fig. 6 - B). A comparable performance of the in-situ gradient formation could be observed.

4. Conclusion

In this study we showed a proof concept of in-situ gradient formation directly from solid buffer components for chromatographic separations. The dosing accuracy is very high and precise operation over a duration of 24 hours suits such a device for gradient elution. By the direct dissolution of buffering agents at the point of use, we can avoid the necessity of the preparation of stock solutions and intermediate hold tanks and thus reduce the facility footprint of chromatographic unit operations significantly. We also think that with this device buffers can be prepared on demand and therefore process materials can be saved. This will not only contribute to better process efficiency but also to sustainability. Especially, considering the amounts of buffer that are prepared in excess to simply avoid supply shortfall. The implementation of a system for the direct in-line dissolution of buffering agents offers a new level of modularity and thus flexibility not achievable by in-line dilution or in-line conditioning.

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Author contribution

Daniel Komuczki: constructed the equipment, conducted the experiments, drafted the manuscript

Nico Lingg: was responsible for gradient design, reviewed and edited the manuscript

Alois Jungbauer: Wrote the research proposal, drafted the manuscript, and helped with interpretation of the data

Peter Satzer: Wrote the control algorithm, help to design the equipment, converted the design into a 3D print

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:[10.1016/j.chroma.2020.461663](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2020.461663).

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